

A proposal for a high-throughput approach to evaluate pollen tube-mediated transformation potential

With the intention of making bioengineering accessible to amateur plant breeders, we propose a methodology to evaluate over 100 liquid formulations *in vitro* that may facilitate germline transformation by their application to the stigma during artificial pollination.

Purpose

Whether through hybrid breeding or genetic engineering, the reshuffling of plant genetic material has led to increased food security, novel medicines, and breathtaking ornamental varieties. Targeted genetic engineering techniques, such as CRISPR and *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation, have the potential to introduce new traits into plants more rapidly. However, despite the growing accessibility of biological experimentation, these methods remain out-of-reach to amateur plant breeders.

Pollen tube-mediated transformation emerged in the 1980s as a method to create transgenic plants by simply applying an exogenous DNA to the cut stigma after pollination. While transformation was successful in some cases, the current accessibility of automated liquid handling systems allows us to explore a much wider set of formulations conducive to pollen tube transformation than originally considered during its emergence. Discovery of a simple formulation that could reliably introduce foreign DNA during the fertilization process would grant any plant enthusiast the ability to uncover new traits without the need of any lab equipment. Further, cost-effective and rapid DNA isolation protocols, in combination with the use of restriction enzymes, can provide amateur breeders with access to DNA fragments without relying on DNA synthesis companies [1].

We aim to perform high-throughput *in vitro* assays on over 100 liquid formulations to identify those that (a) do not interfere with pollen tube extension, (b) reduce nuclease activity, and (c) promote pollen permeability or DNA-pollen tube binding. After initial testing with *Arabidopsis*, we will involve the broader grower community to test pollen from diverse species and determine whether any given formulation could be broadly effective.

Background

Abundant in nature and easy to isolate, pollen has been a prime target for the development of a simple, broadly applicable genetic transformation system. Perhaps more important than its simplicity is its rapidity. Taking advantage of fertilization, the premise of pollen-mediated transformation assumes that the introduction of foreign genetic material into pollen will generate transgenic zygotes. Resulting seeds can further mature and lead to transgenic plants, bypassing the need for tissue culture and drastically reducing the transformation timeline [2]. While promising in theory, the execution of pollen transformation isn't without its difficulties. Nonetheless, existing funding programs continue to recognize pollen as an ideal avenue for achieving expedited, high-yielding, and broadly applicable plant transformations [3].

In vitro pollen transformation methods often result in low efficiencies due to pollen's corrosion-resistant nature. Pollen's outermost layer —the pollen coat— is a hydrophobic layer of lipids and proteins protecting

the grain from water loss and UV light, and playing a vital role in pollen-stigma recognition, adhesion, hydration, and germination [4] [5]. Below the pollen coat lies the exine, an outer layer made up of sporopollenin—a highly crosslinked network of aromatic and aliphatic compounds resistant to physical and chemical degradation. Underneath the exine is the intine—an inner layer akin to the primary cell wall in other plant cells and composed of cellulose, pectin, and hydrolytic enzymes [6] [5]. Most plant species possess an unevenly distributed pollen surface leading to apertures, or certain areas with thinner, structurally modified, or absent exine deposits.

When released from anthers, a pollen grain has lost 15-35% of its water content and is metabolically dormant [7]. In this state, it folds into itself, burying its apertures and exposed intine. As a result, its nearly impenetrable exine layer has intrigued material scientists, but remains an formidable barrier for electroporation- and chemical-based transformation methods [8] [2]. To overcome this difficulty, magnetofection has been leveraged for transient transformation via pollen, though its success has been variable [9] [10].

In an effort to bypass the difficulties of working with *in vitro* pollen transformation, researchers in the 1980s-1990s began to take advantage of natural processes occurring during germination, resulting in the pollen tube pathway transformation method. When pollen comes into contact with a receptive and compatible stigma, pollen adhesion and hydration begins. Water, sugar, and other components needed for germination enter the pollen grain and the internal turgor pressure pushes against the folded exine. In most cases, this expansion leads to exposed apertures through which pollen tubes form and elongate down through the style [6]. In other rare cases, as in the case of *Arabidopsis* and several other cruciferous plants, germination is aperture-independent, as pollen tubes can emerge directly from the pollen wall [11] [12].

With the pollen tube transformation method, a plant's stigma is removed shortly after pollination. An exogenous DNA solution is then directly applied to the cut stigma and the foreign DNA is delivered to the ovary via pollen tube growth, integrating into the genome of the fertilized recipient zygote [13] [14] [15]. Theoretically, DNA doesn't need to enter the pollen. Rather, it can bind to the outer surface of the pollen tube as it grows, leading to its transportation to the ovule. However, due to reproducibility issues, the technique was abandoned in the west but further development continued in China, leading to reports of transgenic plants for cotton, wheat, and other crops by this method [16] [17] [18] [19] [20]. Yet, in many of these cases, the applied DNA solution is only supplemented with sucrose, TE buffer, SSC (sodium chloride and sodium citrate), or Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} cations before its application to the stigma (see Table 1).

DNA solution	References
TE buffer (10mM Tris and 1 mM EDTA)	Luo et al 1989 [15], Li et al 2002 [21]
Sucrose	Wang et al 2001 [22], Wang et al 2010 [23]
Calcium chloride	Hou 2003 [24]
SSC (NaCl and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Na}_3\text{O}_7$ (sodium citrate))	Zhou et al 1983 (Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were also added) [14], Hao et al 2010 [25]

PCR buffer (Tris-HCl, KCl or (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ , and MgCl ₂)	Huang et al 1999 [26], Zhang et al 2009 [17], Wang et al 2019 [16]
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Table 1. Exogenous DNA solution composition of reportedly successful pollen tube transformation efforts.

Even though pollen tube transformation can bypass the need for exogenous DNA to enter the pollen grain, other hurdles must be addressed for DNA to successfully reach the ovule. For example, once hydrated, pollen releases nucleases to degrade foreign DNA [27]. Thus, without the help of nuclease inhibitors within the solution, DNA is at risk of degradation well before reaching the ovule. With a deeper understanding of the morphology and biochemistry of pollen germination, it can be argued that pollen tube-mediated transformation could be further enhanced by including compounds that (a) don't interfere with pollen tube extension, (b) prohibits DNA degradation by nucleases, and (c) promotes a slight increase in intine permeability or facilitates DNA-pollen binding.

The approach

We seek to conceive of and evaluate various liquid formulations that can be applied to the stigma and facilitate germline transformation. Over 100 conditions will be tested *in vitro* on pollen from *Arabidopsis thaliana* to identify which combinatorial effects could lead to a promising transformation formulation. Once the methodology and workflow has been refined, we'll invite amateur breeders and plant enthusiasts to send in pollen to determine whether any solutions are broadly effective.

DNA solution formulations

Tested in 86 species representing 39 plant families, the Brewbaker and Kwack (BK) germination medium effectively supports pollen hydration and tube growth across diverse angiosperms. Sugar, water, calcium, boron, and other essential components enter pollen grains during hydration, thus BK medium consists of roughly 10% sucrose, 100 mg/L boric acid (H₃BO₃), 300 mg/L calcium nitrate (Ca(NO₃)₂), 200 mg/L magnesium sulfate (MgSO₄), and 100 mg/L potassium nitrate (KNO₃) [28] [2]. The tested solutions will be derived from the BK medium and vary in their inclusion of the following components:

Surfactants and solvents

Polysorbate 20 is intended to reduce surface tension and ensure the medium spreads evenly over the stigma. In low concentrations between 0.01-0.05%, there is evidence that polysorbate 20 has little effect on *in vitro* germination. Thus 0.05% of polysorbate 20 will be included in select formulations [29].

Polyethylene glycol (PEG) will serve as an osmo-regulator. Evidence that PEG4000 does not affect pollen germination has been shown for *Cajanus cajan* and *Triticum aestivum* [30] [31]. 10% PEG4000 will be included in select formulations.

Nuclease inhibitors

Aurintricarboxylic Acid (ATA) has been shown to be a broadly effective DNases inhibitor. However, no evidence of its effectiveness in the context of pollen germination was found in the literature, making this the first study to investigate its potential in this application [32].

Conflicting evidence on the ability of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) to decrease nuclease activity was found in the literature [33] [34]. This may be due to a higher concentration of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} ions in pollen hydration and transformation media. EDTA would bind to these cations but remaining cations would still be available for use as cofactors by DNases. Despite the predicted inability of EDTA to suppress nuclease activity in this context, it will be included in initial DNA formulation tests due to its low cost.

Conflicting evidence also exists on whether 5'-ATP can inhibit DNase activity on dsDNA and ssDNA [35] [36]. Because ATP has three negatively charged phosphate groups, it may inhibit nucleases via metal ion chelation. However, its effectiveness and negative charge is dependent on pH. In slightly acidic conditions, ATP is prone to hydrolysis due to increased protonation in the presence of Mg^{2+} in solution. Similar to EDTA, ATP is not expected to effectively inhibit nucleases in this application but will still be included in testing due to its low cost.

We are actively exploring other avenues for nuclease inhibition. For example, non-canonical nucleic acid chemistries may have the ability to escape recognition by nucleases. In the case of mRNA, the replacement of uridine triphosphate with N1-methyl-pseudouridine has been found to increase stability and trigger a lower immunogenicity response [37]. Perhaps non-canonical DNA fragments could evade nucleases released during pollen hydration. If you have suggestions, we'd love to hear your input (see the "Weigh in" section of this proposal).

DNA-pollen tube binding promoters

Chitosan, a cationic polymer derived from chitin, has been found to bind to pectin via electrostatic interactions and DNA due to its negative charge [38] [39] [40]. This biopolymer may facilitate pollen tube-DNA binding to increase the likelihood of foreign DNA reaching the ovule.

Polyamines such as putrescine, spermidine, and spermine have been shown to bind to DNA and pectin [41] [42] [43] [44]. Spermidine has been used in particle bombardment transformation methods to facilitate binding between DNA and microprojectiles such as gold or tungsten particles [45] [46]. Given their ability to bind to DNA and pectin, polyamines may be able to promote DNA-pollen tube binding and reduce nuclease activity. However, polyamine-pectin binding may also prevent foreign DNA from passing deeper into the pollen tube structure. As a result, spermidine will be included in select formulations to determine whether its impact on transformation in this context is positive or negative.

Pollen permeability promoters

Lithium chloride/dimethyl sulfoxide (LiCl-DMSO), often used to dissolve cellulose samples in preparation for NMR spectroscopy or size-exclusion chromatography, will be included in select formulations to slightly disrupt the intine layer [47]. Although there is evidence that low concentrations of DMSO does not inhibit *in vitro* pollen tube extension, no evidence of the impact of LiCl-DMSO on pollen germination has been found in the literature [48].

In select cases, cellulase and pectinase, enzymes that break down cellulose and pectin respectively, will be included to facilitate enzymatic disruption of the intine layer. With their ability to thrive in a slightly lower pH range, acidic cellulases and pectinases can serve as potential pollen permeability promoters [49] [50].

In vitro pollen tube extension, nuclease activity, and DNA uptake assays

Pollen tube extension

Pollen germination interference will be measured by a previously described *in vitro* pollen tube extension assay using Congo Red dye and a 96-well plate imager (λ excitation-470 nm; λ emission-600 nm) [48] [51]. Prepared solutions will be incubated with Congo Red, a dye which binds to polysaccharides in the pollen tube wall. When illuminated with 470 nm light, Congo Red fluoresces. As pollen tube extension occurs, the fluorescence increases because the extended tube provides more polysaccharides for Congo Red to bind.

Plates will be pre-screened without Congo Red to determine if molecules that may cause false positives are present. Six frames per minute over a 9-hour timeframe will be taken to capture change in fluorescence, however this may adjust based on preliminary tests to reduce data storage needs.

Before proceeding to the nuclease activity assay, all formulations will be tested at various concentrations, prepared with the support of an OpenTrons OT-1 liquid handling robot. Formulations that reproducibly interfere with pollen tube extension will not undergo nuclease activity testing. As stigmatic exudates are slightly acidic (pH 4-7), each condition will be tested with three varying pH levels—4.5, 5.5, and 6.5. The tentative plate maps for the initial tests are below, and two identical plates will be tested to normalize for plate-to-plate variability.

		BK Medium (BK)												
		10% sucrose	100 mg/L boric acid (H ₃ BO ₃)	300 mg/L calcium nitrate (Ca(NO ₃) ₂)	200 mg/L magnesium sulfate (MgSO ₄)	100 mg/L potassium nitrate (KNO ₃)								
Plate 1														
		pH 4.5				pH 5.5				pH 6.5				
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
A		BK				BK				BK				Legend
B		BK + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				pH 4.5
C		BK + 10% PEG4000				BK + 10% PEG4000				BK + 10% PEG4000				pH 5.5
D		BK + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				pH 6.5
E		BK + 5 μ M ATA				BK + 5 μ M ATA				BK + 5 μ M ATA				
F		BK + 10 μ M ATA				BK + 10 μ M ATA				BK + 10 μ M ATA				
G		BK + 25 μ M ATA				BK + 25 μ M ATA				BK + 25 μ M ATA				
H		BK + 50 μ M ATA				BK + 50 μ M ATA				BK + 50 μ M ATA				
Plate 2														
		pH 4.5				pH 5.5				pH 6.5				
Row		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
A		BK + 5 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 5 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 5 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				
B		BK + 10 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 10 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 10 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				
C		BK + 25 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 25 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 25 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				
D		BK + 50 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 μ M ATA + 10% PEG4000				
E		BK + 5 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 5 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 5 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				
F		BK + 10 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 10 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 10 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				
G		BK + 25 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 25 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 25 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				
H		BK + 50 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 50 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 50 μ M ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				

Plate 3												
	pH 4.5				pH 5.5				pH 6.5			
Row	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	BK + 5 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 5 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 5 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
B	BK + 10 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 10 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 10 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
C	BK + 25 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 25 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 25 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
D	BK + 50 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 µM ATA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
E	BK + 5 µM EDTA				BK + 5 µM EDTA				BK + 5 µM EDTA			
F	BK + 10 µM EDTA				BK + 10 µM EDTA				BK + 10 µM EDTA			
G	BK + 25 µM EDTA				BK + 25 µM EDTA				BK + 25 µM EDTA			
H	BK + 50 µM EDTA				BK + 50 µM EDTA				BK + 50 µM EDTA			

Plate 4												
	pH 4.5				pH 5.5				pH 6.5			
Row	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	BK + 5 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 5 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 5 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000			
B	BK + 10 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 10 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 10 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000			
C	BK + 25 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 25 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 25 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000			
D	BK + 50 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 µM EDTA + 10% PEG4000			
E	BK + 5 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 5 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 5 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20			
F	BK + 10 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 10 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 10 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20			
G	BK + 25 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 25 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 25 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20			
H	BK + 50 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 50 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 50 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20			

Plate 5												
	pH 4.5				pH 5.5				pH 6.5			
Row	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	BK + 5 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 5 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 5 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
B	BK + 10 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 10 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 10 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
C	BK + 25 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 25 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 25 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
D	BK + 50 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 µM EDTA + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
E	BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP				BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP				BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP			
F	BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP				BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP				BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP			
G	BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP				BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP				BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP			
H	BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP				BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP				BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP			

Plate 6												
	pH 4.5				pH 5.5				pH 6.5			
Row	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20			
B	BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20			
C	BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20			
D	BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20				BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20			
E	BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000				BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000				BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000			
F	BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000			
G	BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000				BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000				BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000			
H	BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000				BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000				BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP + 10% PEG4000			

Plate 7												
	pH 4.5				pH 5.5				pH 6.5			
Row	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 20 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
B	BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 50 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
C	BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 100 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
D	BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000				BK + 500 µM 5'-ATP + 0.05% Polysorbate 20 + 10% PEG4000			
E												
F												

Nuclease activity

To determine nuclease activity, [PicoGreen](#), a dsDNA-binding dye, will be added to each solution and fluorescence decay will be measured with a 96-well plate imager. When bound to dsDNA, PicoGreen will fluoresce (λ excitation-480 nm; λ emission-520 nm). If nucleases are present and active, they're expected to degrade dsDNA over time, decreasing the number of PicoGreen-bound dsDNA and reducing the total emitted fluorescence. Five frames per second over a 3-hour timeframe will be taken to capture fluorescence decay.

Based on the results of the pollen tube extension and nuclease activity assays, select formulations will proceed to DNA-pollen tube binding testing.

DNA-pollen tube binding

Formulations containing DNA fragments will be centrifuged at 500-800 RPM for 5 minutes to pellet the pollen. The supernatant, containing unbound DNA and extra reagents, will be discarded. The pollen pellet will be resuspended in TE buffer, centrifuged again, and resuspended in a PCR master mix to prepare for real-time PCR. Detection and amplification of the DNA fragment would indicate successful DNA-pollen tube binding.

Weigh in

Plant breeders and biologists alike are encouraged to publicly share their feedback on the strength of the experimental design and the usefulness of a simple solution to create transgenic plants during artificial pollination. Depending on the results from initial tests and our ability to refine the methodology, we may invite the community to send in pollen from different species to get a better sense of successful solutions. If you're an amateur breeder or grower and you'd like to send in pollen for testing, please email jasbneal@gmail.com and we'll get back to you quickly.

1. For amateur breeders and plant enthusiasts: What are the most important factors that would affect whether you adopt a plant transformation tool or methodology? What would make you hesitant to use a plant transformation tool or methodology?
2. Are there other compounds that could serve as nuclease inhibitors, DNA-pollen tube binding promoters, or pollen permeability promoters? We're especially interested in hearing about other broad-acting nuclease inhibitors to potentially test.
3. While feasible in theory, the DNA-pollen tube binding assay may not be the best way to test whether the addition of certain compounds promote DNA-pollen tube binding. For example, PicoGreen will not reveal the presence of bound ssDNA and centrifugation could remove lightly bound DNA. Further, qPCR will fail to detect the uptake of DNA by pollen, and bound fragments that may have been cut by nucleases and are "unrecognizable" to PCR primers would also remain undetected. Are there ways to refine this assay or determine DNA-pollen tube binding without a fluorescence microscope?
4. High-throughput screening of this nature will produce large datasets. Are there specific statistical analyses or data structuring considerations that should be taken into account?

Contributors

1. Jasmine Neal: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing
2. Atanas Radkov: Critical feedback
3. Shane Simonsen: Conceptualization, Critical feedback

ChatGPT-4o and o1 were used for editing and to translate Development of Transgenic Wheat by Hou et al 2003.

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